

COMMON TRENDS IN EARLY CAREER GUIDANCE IN PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS IN KAZAKHSTAN AND TURKEY

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Abstract. *Until today, there has been an increasing importance of guidance and psychological counseling services in preschool organizations in the right direction in discovering children's interests and abilities and in their professional development. Guidance and counseling services in educational institutions include efforts to help children in a planned, programmatic way that is used to develop their physical, mental and social abilities and potential at the highest possible level. To assume the role of the bridge in the transition process from kindergarten to life. Career counseling services serve a guiding function by helping children choose the right profession according to their abilities and interests and become successful later in life, first by getting to know themselves, and then by getting to know the child's family and teacher.. The aim of this study is to show the effect of career education and counseling on the communicative and professional development of a child, which is a new application and career field. In addition, the study is the definition of comparative activity indicators in vocational education and training in preschool institutions in Turkey and preschool education in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Including recommendations related to educational services in Turkey and some exemplary practices in the world.*

Keywords: *career development, career counseling, preschool, child development, family relations with children*

XXI the century is expressed as a period of great and rapid changes in the social, individual, political and economic fields due to technological development and globalization. Therefore, it is becoming increasingly difficult for individuals to adapt to these changes, manage competition and turn changes into advantages in their careers. Considering this effort at the adult individual level, the ability of children and young people to adapt to these changes and make healthy and productive decisions about life makes career education and counseling services at the professional level even more mandatory through family-school-state cooperation. changes in economic, social and technological aspects are forcing educational institutions to ensure that children and young people successfully transition from school to business life and their demands during this transition process. Therefore, in the new world order, educational institutions should design their programs from the primary school stage in order to create a productive educational environment that will introduce children and young people to real life and ensure a successful transition from school to business life. When we look at the literature and practices on the subject in our country, the subject of career education and counseling is mostly evaluated at the high school level and in relation to university exams. Opinions on the necessity of evaluating the career choice issue, which is one of the most important decisions of an individual's life, from primary education are limited and fall into recent times. Therefore, it is necessary to disseminate these views and to address the issue at a more academic level. However, the decisions taken by the elementary guidance and counseling services center in our country on this issue and the developments such as the launch of the framework program are also pleasing. The aim of this study is to shed light on the importance of launching career education and counseling services from the primary school period for children to

create their future plans. In the study, the factors affecting career counseling services at the primary school level, the personal development of the child and the career development process, career counseling practices and the short- and long-term results of the career counseling process are evaluated within the framework of a model.

1-Picture. Kazakhstan kindergarten

2-Picture. Turkish kindergarten

The study is complemented by recommendations on the effectiveness of career counseling services at the primary school level. I . Career Counseling and Guidance Services in Primary Education Guidance and counseling services in educational institutions cover efforts to help students in a planned, programmatic way to develop their physical, mental and social capacity and potential at the most advanced level by taking on the role of a bridge in the process of transition from school to life. Career counseling constitutes an important field in these services and assumes a guiding function by mediating children's ability to choose the right profession in accordance with their abilities and interests and to succeed in later life, first by getting to know themselves, and then by getting to know the child through the family and the teacher. Career counseling appears to us as an important service area of school counseling. Career counseling by a simple definition is “an interpersonal process designed to guide individuals' career development problems” (Osborn and Baggerly, 2004:46). The American School Counselors Organization (ASCA, 1997) has

defined career development as a basic service area within comprehensive guidance programs, because such services are 120 Bu it can be stated that the modern understanding on the subject is that conducting education and career counseling services together will contribute to making more informed choices for the child. The European Community's report entitled “Educational and Vocational Counseling” defines nine areas of activity as elements of educational and career counseling (<http://www.insankaynaklari.com> , 22.03.2005): Providing information: Providing objective and realistic data. (For example, the available field options, course topics, training programs, or job opportunities, etc. evaluation: Making an assessment using formal and informal techniques (tests, exams, interviews) that accurately diagnoses an individual's suitability for a particular option. Making suggestions: Making suggestions based on the consultant's own knowledge and experience. Guiding: Helping individuals to explore their own thoughts and feelings about their own situations, the possibilities that are open, the approximate consequences of their choices. Career education: Presenting a program of planned experiences to develop skills, concepts and knowledge that can enable individuals to make appropriate career choices. (Discussions on resume writing, study workshops; small exams about job interviews, role-playing, interview exercises; visits to domestic and foreign companies, internships or work observations) Placement: Helping candidates get into a specific job, a specific course of education or upbringing, work observations or internships. Defense: Negotiating directly with institutions in favor of certain individuals (especially for candidates who have experience barriers to entering a certain education or job, or who are at risk of not being accepted). Feedback: Informing educational institutions and other service providers about the types of courses and training programs required by employers and individuals, but not currently offered. Follow-up mentoring: Contacting them to see the latest status of the individuals they have previously served and providing assistance if necessary. As it can be seen, although career management, guidance and psychological counseling and educational fields are actually similar fields that evaluate human beings as the main field of study, there is a lack of interdisciplinary research and applications in this regard. Other problems experienced in this specialty are; lack of policy and resources on the subject at the national level, lack of integrity and vision, general lack of coordination and structuring related to the profession, etc. it can be sorted as According to Betz, the importance of education for children's career development is not adequately understood. (Betz, 1993:674) In this regard, developmental career education has been developed in Australia by the Australian Council of Education under the umbrella of the course curriculum program in order to give the necessary value to career education. In this study, it is suggested that the integration of career education with the curriculum should be included for all students – from elementary school to high school. (Australian Education Council 1992; 12.) In this way, students can relate what they have learned to real-life career fields, make individual career planning more consciously, and teachers can also turn to an educational approach that is not far from the dynamics and demands of real business life. Children need opportunities to explore mental, emotional images and impressions about themselves, other individuals and life, and support to be able to turn identities related to themselves and their professions into reality in their minds. Career planning is a long-term field that involves a wide period of time rather than a short-term effort. Launching career planning and development services from an early age is an important issue in order for individuals to be successful and make the right choices during the education that prepares them for career life. When the related services and effectiveness of schools are examined, it is seen that most of them carry out these services with random, unscheduled and short-term solutions rather than structured, conscious and long-term efforts. This situation, on the other hand,

affects the more efficient use of individual life at the micro level, as well as the saving of budgets and resources allocated to education at the macro level.

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